

MANUFACTURING TECHNOLOGY OF WOUND STRUCTURES BY TRANSFORMATION OF WOUND PREFORMS

Abel S. Cherevatsky¹

¹ *Department of Composite Materials, Israel Military Industries Limited
P.O. Box 1044/66, Ramat Hasharon, 47100, Israel*

SUMMARY: In the present work the transformation approach is developed to manufacture some fiber-reinforced structures which couldn't be wound directly. A procedure of determining an appropriate wound preform structure that could be transformed into the given structure before curing is suggested. This approach is implemented to find a wound preform for a cone structure which reinforcing fibers are in an equilibrium state under the internal pressure. Three different solutions are discussed: the wound preform whose base diameter coincides with the base diameter of the structure, the wound preform whose top opening is equal to the top opening of the cone structure, and a vessel with equal openings as wound preform, whose top part may be transformed into a given cone structure.

KEYWORDS: geodetic trajectories, cone structure, wound preform, transformation procedure.

INTRODUCTION

Filament winding technology is one of the most economically advantageous manufacturing techniques for producing thin composite elements of different constructions. This is accomplished by the machine laying of resin impregnated fiber filaments onto a mandrel of an element, followed by curing and mandrel removal procedures. During the winding procedure the equilibrium equations of filaments on the mandrel surface must be fulfilled. These equations reduce the multitude of realizable filament trajectories to the set of geodetic or "near-geodetic" trajectories. To create a wound layer which fully and uniformly covers the mandrel surface means to find a continuous chain of winding trajectories covering the mandrel with equal overlapping. These chains were found only for a determined kind of surfaces, among them - rotational surfaces. In addition, only convex or plane trajectories may be realized on the mandrel. So, filament winding technology provides only special kinds of wound structures on the set of realizable mandrel surfaces.

One of the essential advantages of composite materials is the possibility to create optimally their internal structure according to the stress-strain state of manufacturing elements. This

possibility arises during the manufacturing process and is based on the variation of winding angles of the filaments as reinforcements of composite structure in the most loaded directions. But usually, the trajectories of optimal reinforcements are not “near-geodetic” and so they can't be wound: each filament being put along these trajectories will slip off the mandrel.

The filaments being put in optimal directions will keep an equilibrium state if they are put on the mandrel as a complete net. In this case the slipping friction is not determined by friction between resin impregnated filaments, but by essentially greater friction between filaments in the knots of the net. The way of manufacture of the optimal reinforcement structure on a given surface may be found, if such an appropriate surface with “near-geodetic” wound structure exists, that may be transformed into a given surface so that wound filaments will transform into the optimal reinforcements. An appropriate wound surface will be called - wound preform, the optimal reinforcement structure on the given surface will be called - a given structure, and the procedure of transforming the preform into the given structure will be called - transformation procedure.

The solution of two sequential problems must be found to provide the possibility of a transformation procedure for a given structure:

Problem 1: To find an appropriate wound preform for a given structure.

Problem 2: To describe the possible transformations of the found preform into a given structure and to choose a transformation based on technologically realizable loads, applied to the wound net during transformation.

GEOMETRY OF TRANSFORMATION, GENERAL EQUATIONS

Let us suppose that all fiber nets to be considered consist of two different families of inextensible fibers. The fibers of the same family have no intersections and fiber from one family can't slip along the fibers from the other family. If the geometrical equation for the middle surface of the given structure is:

$$\bar{r} = \bar{r}(\alpha^1, \alpha^2), \quad (1)$$

the corresponding metric tensor is determined by:

$$\begin{aligned} g_{ij} &= g_{ij}(\alpha^1, \alpha^2) = \bar{r}_i \bar{r}_j \\ \bar{r}_i &= \partial \bar{r} / \partial \alpha^i, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where

α^1, α^2 - gaussian coordinates on the given structure which have been chosen so that corresponding coordinate net coincides with the given fiber net,

g_{ij} - components of the metric tensor on the given structure,

\bar{r} - radius - vector of the middle surface of the given structure.

The geometrical equation of the middle surface of unknown preform is looking for as:

$$\bar{R} = t(z)\bar{e}(\psi) + z\bar{k} \quad (3)$$

where

z, ψ - cylindrical coordinates on the preform,

\bar{e}, \bar{k} - unit axes vectors of cylindrical coordinate system,

t - radius of the preform's cross-section,

\bar{R} - radius - vector of the preform.

To determine a bijective differentiable mapping of the given structure's middle surface to the preform's given surface means to determine the following unknown mapping:

$$z = z(\alpha^i), \psi = \psi(\alpha^i) . \quad (4)$$

The inextensibility of fibers during transformation is supposed and hence two components of preform and given structure metric tensors must be equal:

$$G_{11} = g_{11}, \quad G_{22} = g_{22} , \quad (5)$$

where $G_{ij} = G_{ij}(\alpha^k)$ - components of preform surface metric tensor.

The coordinate lines $\alpha^1 = \text{const}$, $\alpha^2 = \text{const}$ are geodesics on the preform, so two differential equations on the preform surface must be fulfilled (Ref. 1):

$$\begin{aligned} 2 g_{11} \frac{\partial G_{12}}{\partial \alpha^1} - G_{12} \frac{\partial g_{11}}{\partial \alpha^1} - g_{11} \frac{\partial g_{11}}{\partial \alpha^2} &= 0 , \\ 2 g_{22} \frac{\partial G_{12}}{\partial \alpha^2} - G_{12} \frac{\partial g_{22}}{\partial \alpha^2} - g_{22} \frac{\partial g_{22}}{\partial \alpha^1} &= 0 . \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

G_{12} component of the preform metric tensor may be found from Eqn 6 if compatibility condition for Eqn 6 is fulfilled.

If metric tensor $G_{ij}(\alpha^k)$ on the preform surface has been found, the geometry of the preform ($t(z)$ - meridian of the preform, $z = z(\alpha^k)$, $\psi = \psi(\alpha^k)$ - coordinate geodesic lines on the preform) may be determined from the following equations:

$$\left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial \alpha^i} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial t}{\partial \alpha^i} \right)^2 + t^2 \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \alpha^i} \right)^2 = G_{ii} , \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\partial t}{\partial \alpha^1} \frac{\partial t}{\partial \alpha^2} + \frac{\partial z}{\partial \alpha^1} \frac{\partial z}{\partial \alpha^2} + t^2 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \alpha^1} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \alpha^2} = G_{12} ,$$

$$i = 1, 2$$

Let us consider an axisymmetric given structure: an axisymmetric surface with a net, formed by rotation of two meridian symmetric curves around the central axis of the surface. For general axisymmetric given structures the following solution of the Eqn 6,7 was found (see Ref. 2):

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_{11} &= G_{22} = G (\alpha^1 - \alpha^2) , \\
 G_{12} &= -G + c\sqrt{G} , \\
 \psi &= (\alpha^1 + \alpha^2) / 2 , \\
 t &= \sqrt{2 c \sqrt{G}} ,
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 z &= \int \sqrt{G - \frac{c\sqrt{G}}{2} - \frac{cG^{-\frac{3}{2}}}{8} \left(\frac{dG}{d\lambda}\right)^2} d\lambda , \\
 \lambda &= \alpha^1 - \alpha^2 ,
 \end{aligned}$$

where C - an arbitrary constant.

DETERMINATION OF CONE STRUCTURE TO BE WOUND

The form of the given structure is a truncated cone with height H , base radius R , pole opening radius T and a meridian line in cylindrical coordinates:

$$\tilde{r}(z) = R - \tilde{z} \frac{(R-T)}{H} , \tag{9}$$

see Fig. 1. The given net on the cone has been chosen so that it is in an equilibrium state under internal pressure and axial load. In particular, a given net may keep an unformable state being impregnated by low modulus elastic resin like rubber, and would attain a cone form under internal pressure and axial load. The winding angle of such a cone net is determined according to Ref. 3:

$$\cos^2 \tilde{\varphi} = \frac{\tilde{r}^2 - T^2 + Q}{3\tilde{r}^2 - T^2 + Q} , \tag{10}$$

where $Q = P / \pi q$,

P - axial force,

q - internal pressure,

$\pm \tilde{\varphi}$ - winding angle.

Above determined cone structure is an axisymmetric structure. In an appropriate coordinate system with a coordinate net coinciding with the fiber net, introduced in Eqn 10, the metric tensor components have been calculated:

$$g_{11} = g_{22} = G = \frac{3}{8} \tilde{t}^2 + \frac{(Q - T^2)}{8}. \quad (11)$$

So, wound preform for this structure may be found using Eqn 8.

**WOUND PREFORM WHOSE BASE
DIAMETER COINCIDES WITH THE BASE DIAMETER
OF THE CONE STRUCTURE**

For this wound preform an arbitrary constant c from Eqn 8 is found using the given value of its base diameter:

$$c = R^2 / (2\sqrt{G(R)}). \quad (12)$$

The results of the calculation of the meridian line of the preform for cone structure are given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Preform and cone structures meridians: 1- cone structure meridian, 2- preform structure meridian.

Received wound preforms in this option are essentially shorter than given cones and have greater pole openings. Axial force is a necessary load component to realize their transformation in the cones. During transformation the base section of the preform must be

clamped, see Fig. 2. The winding angle of the preform at the pole opening is less than 90 degrees, and so an auxiliary fitting must be added to the pole of the preform. Another option is to wind the preform structure on pins located at the pole area.

Fig. 2: Transformation scheme of the wound preform into the cone structure.

**WOUND PREFORM WHOSE TOP
OPENING COINCIDES WITH THE TOP OPENING
OF THE CONE STRUCTURE**

Let us find the wound preform with the top opening being equal to the top opening of the cone, that may be transformed to the cone structure by internal pressure only. In this option an arbitrary constant of Eqn 8 is equal to:

$$c = T \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}. \tag{13}$$

Some examples of calculated preform meridian lines are given in Fig. 3:

Fig. 3: Preform and cone structures meridians: 1- cone structure meridian, 2- preform structure meridian.

In this option the winding angle of the preform at the pole opening is less than 90 degrees, and the pole opening must be closed for transmitting an internal pressure, so an auxiliary fitting must be added in the pole opening of the preform, see Fig. 4. The base diameter of the preform is less than the cone base diameter and must be expanded during transformation. An expanding ring may give an appropriate technical solution for such procedure, see Fig.4.

Fig.4: Transformation procedure for cone wound preform without changing the top pole opening.

CONE VESSEL WITH EQUAL OPENINGS AS WOUND PREFORM

Apparently, there are some technological advantages in the preform, formed as a vessel with two equal pole openings. This vessel would be wound by a traditional filament winding technique and its upper part would be transformed into the given cone by internal pressure. To find such a preform using our approach, the given cone structure (see Eqn 9,10) must be previously modified to a cone vessel with equal pole openings, see Fig. 5. The added bottom part of this vessel is called a dome.

If $\tilde{t}(z)$ - an equation of a dome meridian line, the winding angle $\tilde{\varphi}$ on the dome is determined according to Ref. 3:

$$\operatorname{tg}^2 \tilde{\varphi} = \frac{2a - b}{a}, \quad (14)$$

and

$$G = \frac{\tilde{t}^2}{4} \left(1 + \frac{a}{2a - b} \right), \quad (15)$$

where

$$a = \left(1 + \left(\frac{d\tilde{t}}{dz} \right)^2 \right)^2, \quad b = \tilde{t} \frac{d^2 \tilde{t}}{dz^2} \left(\frac{d\tilde{t}}{dz} \right)^2, \quad (16)$$

$0 \leq z \leq H_d$, H_d - height of the dome, see Fig. 5.

$\tilde{t}(z)$ function must satisfy five conditions of continuity:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{t}(0) &= R, \\ \frac{d\tilde{t}}{dz}(0) &= -\frac{R - T}{H}, \\ \frac{d^2 \tilde{t}}{dz^2}(0) &= 0, \\ \frac{d^3 \tilde{t}}{dz^3}(0) &= 0, \\ \tilde{t}(H) &= T, \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

and a sixth condition of poles identity:

$$b(H) = 0. \tag{18}$$

To satisfy six conditions of Eqn 17,18 function $\tilde{t}(z)$ was found as a polynomial function of the fifth order. The example of found preform for cone vessel structure is given in Fig.5.

Fig. 5: Meridians of preform and cone vessels: 1- cone vessel meridian, 2- preform vessel meridian.

The transformation procedure of preform vessel is demonstrated in Fig. 6:

Fig. 6: Transformation procedure for cone vessel wound preform.

CONCLUSIONS

The preform transformation approach in manufacturing of wound structures is suggested. General geometric equations describing at unknown preforms for axisymmetric given structures are derived. As examples, three different wound preforms for axisymmetrical equilibrium under internal pressure cone structure was found. This cone structure couldn't be wound by traditional filament winding technology.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Many thanks to Mandy Buyum for his continuous help in all MATLAB calculations that were done during this investigation.

REFERENCES

1. Hsiung, C.C., *A First Course in Differential Geometry*, Pure and applied mathematics, A Wiley-Interscience publication, 1981.
2. Cherevatsky, A.S., "Geometric Aspects of the Transformation Method in the Manufacturing of the Wound Structures", *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, No. 5, 1990, pp. 917-922, (in Russian).
3. Segal, V.L., Cherevatsky, S.B., "The Fiber Nets on the Surface", *Proceedings of the Sixth USSR Conference on Theory of Plates and Shells*, Baku, 1966, pp. 680-684, (in Russian).